

EARTH SCIENCES

NANOTECHNOLOGY IN ECOLOGY

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Abstract

To date, nanoscale materials are very in demand and are used in the most diverse areas of modern science and technology. This class of materials has completely new properties, which makes it possible to create new devices that will be more effective. Given such a variety of properties of nanomaterials, the question arises as to the possibility of using them for environmental protection, since this problem has now become global and it needs to be addressed. It is supposed that with the help of nanomaterials it will be possible to improve the environmental situation for the better, either directly, for example, detecting or removing existing contaminants, and indirectly, by inventing materials that will be harmless to the world around them. [7]

Keywords: nanotechnology in ecology, nanomaterials, ecology.

Introduction. Nanomaterials are materials created using nanoparticles or using nanotechnology and having unique properties. Nanotechnologies are actively used in medicine, pharmaceuticals, mechanical engineering, industry, agriculture, biology, electronics, and ecology. They make it possible to create tiny materials, control them at the atomic and molecular level and produce devices whose size does not exceed 100 nanometers.

The use of nanotechnology in ecology is associated with the creation of new highly efficient insulating materials. For example, the lack of clean water is a major environmental problem, especially in developing countries with military conflicts and frequent natural disasters. Population growth and intensive agriculture

are associated with the ever-increasing consumption of clean water, so the search for new methods of its purification is becoming increasingly urgent. The use of nanomaterials can help improve existing ones, as well as create completely new technologies and materials used for water purification.

Nanofiltration is becoming one of the main processes for water purification, in particular to soften and remove ions or organic compounds from water. The peculiarity of nanomembranes to selectively remove “unnecessary” particles or ions makes it possible to use such filters in various fields and for various purposes. The functional properties of nanofilters strongly depend on which nanoparticles are used, for example, on the composition or morphology. (picture1)

Picture 1. Nanotechnology in ecology.

There are problems with using modern filters. One of them is contamination of the filter with chemicals or microorganisms, and quite quickly. However, with the help of nanofilters it will be possible to avoid such situations. For example, silver nanoparticles can be used to avoid biofouling of the filter. It has been proven that it only takes 60 minutes to completely destroy particles

that come into contact with a filter coated with silver nanoparticles. [1]

Pollution of surface and ground waters with various highly toxic chemicals, heavy metals, etc. This is a very serious world problem. Adsorption nanomaterials are used to reduce pollution levels.

In order to remove mercury ions from water, a polypyrrole/depleted graphene oxide composite can be

used. It has been proven that the use of sheets of this composite with a thickness of 1.34 nm makes it possible to selectively remove mercury ions from water with an adsorption capacity of 980 mg/g.

Iron nanoparticles can adsorb chromium ions from solution with much greater efficiency than the substances used. The acidity of the medium greatly affects the absorption efficiency: for example, at pH = 4, the adsorption capacity is 31.5 mg/g, and at pH = 7 – 23.3 mg/g. Another key feature is the easy ability to reuse nanoparticle data.

In order to remove various metal ions from water, magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles can be used. The average particle size was 21 nm. Depending on the acidity and temperature of the medium, the adsorption efficiency of various metal ions changes. It varies from 35 to 100%. In order for the removal of metal ions to be complete, a multi-stage installation can be used, while

changing the acidity and temperature of the medium. [2.5]

Aluminum oxide nanoparticles with a particle size on average of about 40 nm can adsorb formaldehyde quite effectively. If the acidity of the medium is from 5 to 8.5, then formaldehyde is removed from the water by 100%. In addition, these particles can also be used to adsorb formaldehyde from a water stream. The removal of oil and petroleum products from water can also be achieved using nanoparticles. This can be done using a nanocomposite.

The efficiency of various adsorption nanomaterials is much greater than that of the materials used today. The examples discussed confirm this. The reason for this is that the specific surface area is very important for adsorption. Since this value for nanoparticles is quite large, the efficiency will be significantly higher compared to other materials. (picture 2,3)

Picture 2. Dependence of adsorption efficiency on pH of the medium

Picture 3. Dependence of adsorption efficiency on medium temperature

With the development of nanotechnology, we need to understand that nanomaterials can cause environmental pollution. Nanomaterials can influence the environment based on their special properties and behavior at the nanoscale. Here are a few aspects to consider:

1. Toxicity and Biocompatibility: Some nanomaterials may be toxic to living organisms. It is important to study their effects on biological systems. On the other hand, there are also biocompatible nanomaterials that can be used for medical purposes without negative effects on the body.

2. Distribution in the Environment: Nanomaterials can be distributed in the environment, including soil, water and air. This can occur either as a result of industrial processes or due to the use of products containing nanomaterials.

3. Accumulation in Organisms: Nanomaterials can be absorbed by organisms and accumulate in their tissues. This can cause various biological effects and have consequences for ecosystems.

4. Changing the Properties of Substances: Nanoscale changes in the chemical structure of materials can lead to changes in their properties. This may affect

their behavior in the environment and interaction with other chemical components.

5. Environmental Safety of Production: Nanomaterial production processes can also have an impact on the environment. Effective waste management and minimizing environmental impacts play an important role in the development of sustainable nanotechnology.

Research in this area aims to better understand the effects of nanomaterials and develop methods for their safe use. This includes research in nanotoxicology and ecotoxicology, as well as the development of standards and regulation for nanomaterials.

Some nanoparticles can threaten nature and human health. Therefore, experts are trying to attract public attention not only to the prospects, but also to the likely risks. [3]

Cleaning the environment from nanoparticles is a serious problem, since they are absorbed by plants and transported by wind over vast distances. Scientists have discovered that iron oxide nanoparticles accelerate the movement of man-made lead in the air. And nano-sized aluminum oxide particles interfere with plant growth.

The size of nanoparticles allows them to penetrate the body through breathing and even through the skin. They enter the bloodstream and accumulate in cells, disrupting their functioning. People working with nanomaterials are most at risk.

In addition to monitoring industrial safety, government agencies need to provide training for specialists who will assess the risks associated with nanotechnology. International and national occupational safety and health systems should also include methods to measure the degree of impact of nanomaterials on the

health of people involved in their production, transportation, use and disposal.

In addition, it is necessary to ensure that the factories where nanomaterials are produced do not worsen the environmental situation and do not harm the health of people living in close proximity to them. [4,6]

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